

HISTORY OF TOURIST AND PREHISTORIC HERITAGES LOCATED IN SURKHANDARYA REGION.

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Abstract: This article reveals the information about the location, importance and history of historical and touristic objects located in Surkhonadarya region. We can also see the influence of such buildings on the development of tourism in Surkhandarya and how they are preserved now.

Key Words: Tourism, Heritage Site, Father Termiz, Isa at Termizi shrine, Kokildar father, Sultan Saodat, Kirqqiz, Jarqòrdon tower, prehistoric and ancient, structure, annual income.

In ancient times, our grandparents conducted many scientific researches. They also carried out their scientific work within a certain area or in the places where they live. As a result of their research, today we have a great legacy from history, and historical buildings are named after them so that the names of great people will not be lost, and the younger generations will remember them. On the other hand, other historical monuments located in our country are named because of their unique history. For example, the original name of Termiz Ota is Hakim at Termizi, this shrine is named after a person. The Qorqqiz shrine has a special history of getting such a name. We will consider such interesting facts in our article.

Clearly that Termizi architectural complex , Hakim Termizi mausoleum - an architectural monument in Termiz (9th - 15th centuries). Al Hakim al-Tirmizi mausoleum, which is sacred for Muslims, is located on the outskirts of the ancient city of Termiz. Abu Abdullah ibn Hasan ibn Bashir al-Hakimi al-Tirmizi, a great Islamic figure, the author of various philosophical and religious works, the creator of the dervish community, is buried in the mausoleum. The complex is associated with the name of Abu Abdullah Muhammad Hakim Termizi (about 750-760 Termiz - 869). In this mausoleum is the grave of Termizi. Termizi architectural complex was rebuilt several times over the centuries. Today, this complex is one of the main pilgrimage destinations for oases and regional guests. It consisted of buildings such as a mosque , a mausoleum , a hall , and a monastery . The total area of the complex is 28.0x29.0 meters, of which the

mausoleum

is 5.10x4.70 meters [1] . It is said that a house was built from raw bricks (9th century) and Hakim Termizi lived and taught there . A part of the wide courtyard , a thick wall fence and a small cellar-like room in the northeast corner of the building have been preserved. Over time , a mausoleum was built over the grave , in the south-west corner of the room, made of raw brick, facing south (9th century). Termizi's mausoleum is glorified among the people as a saint 's grave, a sacred place of pilgrimage . Later, attached to the eastern wall of the mausoleum, a small shrine and the mausoleum of his son alHakim Abdullah (10th century), a 3-domed prayer mosque (11-12th centuries) facing a small courtyard in the north (11-12th centuries) and a number of additional rooms were added. In the territory of the At-Termizi complex, there are also chilla houses. These chill rooms are a historical cave structure dating back to the VX centuries AD [2] . The complex is popularly known as Termiz-ota. According to the legend, when he was ten years old, a vision came to him and an old man gave him knowledge. Over time, Termizi gained fame, but continued to live modestly in his parents' house. Hakim al-Tirmizi died as a martyr - the enemies who invaded the city in his old age cut him off from the beginning (end of the 9th century). According to legend, Genghis Khan was amazed by this unique masterpiece and ordered his army not to damage the monument, because he believed that this building was not created by humans, but by gods. A dome is raised above the mausoleum, and inside the building there are very luxurious decorations. The tombstone of the saint, made of marble and decorated with unique patterns and Arabic inscriptions, attracts attention. Next to the ensemble is a Jame Mosque, which was built a little later. There are several other

interesting attractions in the territory of the At-Termizi complex: Chillakhanol - ancient cave structures dating back to the 5th century AD, the ruins of the ancient town of Tarmita (Old Termiz), the city of Termiz and the city museum of Termiz. During the rule of the Timurids (15th century), the house was rebuilt from brick on a high foundation (height 1.5 m). Repair work on Termizi mausoleum was carried out in 1996 in connection with the 660th anniversary of the birth of Amir Temur.

Second monument is The Tomb of Termizi, Tomb of Abu Isa Termizi is an architectural monument located in Sherabad district of Surkhandarya region (11th - 12th centuries). The mausoleum was built over the grave of the famous Muhaddith Abu Isa Muhammad At-Tirmidhi [2] [3]. At-Tirmizi mausoleum is part of Hakim at-Tirmizi complex. Apart from this mausoleum, there are buildings such as a mosque, a monastery, and a monastery in the complex. This complex has been restored several times over the years. Adjacent to the eastern wall of the mausoleum, a tomb was built. Also, near the mausoleum, the mausoleum of Hakim al-Tirmizi's son al-Hakim Abdullah was built in the 10th century. In the 11th and 12th centuries, a three-domed prayer mosque was also built. During the reign of the Timurids (15th century), the house was rebuilt from baked bricks to a height of one and a half meters. The adjacent rooms have been renovated. The mihrab located in the western part of the mosque was built in the same period. The mausoleum was repaired during the reign of Abdullah Khan (1583-1598). A new nine-domed mosque was built in the yard. A simple porch is also installed at the entrance. Another small mausoleum and shrine was built at the entrance from the south. Also, this mausoleum is interconnected with the al-Tirmizi mausoleum and the khanaqah through vaulted partitions.

Today, the monument is in the form of a single building consisting of 4 rooms (compartments) passing through arches, the size of the rooms is 4.3 x 4.5 meters. The northeastern style was later blocked due to the construction of the porch. The 3-room compartment has a murabba layout, the southern one is a cave. It has a marble ceiling. Sagana is 3-step, decorated with muqarnas patterns and inscriptions. From the cave, you can go to the room through a long narrow passage. The floor of the room is lower than that of the cave, and they are separated by a wide arch. The room has a dome roof and is furnished in a loving way. From the 2 rooms next to it, it is opened in the northeast style. The 3 porches in front of the hall are domed, shield-shaped, and the walls are decorated with 4 archways, and the frames are made of baked bricks. Termizi's mausoleum was decorated with hankkori decorations, and 6 brick arches were made on its outer walls. White ganch fences are installed on the walls. The porches are framed in brick thickness. Termizi's mausoleum is dominated by a small dome-shaped structure [5].

The next one is Kyrgyz Castle - the first Islamic Academy for girls in Uzbekistan - an architectural monument located in Surkhandarya region (9th - 10th centuries). It was preserved in ruins in Termiz district. There is no information about what purpose it was built for (castle, palace, house, caravanserai). Researchers have different hypotheses about the function of this monument. A nobleman's palace outside the city, a girls' madrasah, a house, a caravanserai and other assumptions are reported. The fact that it was located outside the city of Termiz in the Middle Ages indicates that the castle served as a fortress outside the city. It was created in a strictly embodied way, according to the aspects of the world. "Termizi Mausoleum" UzME. Letter T Volume One. Tashkent, 2000. The Kyrgyz fortress was built by the Somonites in the 9th century. Craftsmen brought from Iran and India took part in the construction of the castle. During the Mongol attack in the 12th-13th centuries, the second floor of the building was demolished. This castle was rebuilt several times during the 9th-15th centuries [1].

According to oral legend, the heroic girl Guloyim, who was able to repulse the attack of the enemies mentioned in folk epics, and her 40 friends lived here. According to another legend, the ruler who has 40 wives wants to marry the 41st woman. He buried 40 women who resisted him alive in this castle. Locals believe that the castle served as the first girls' academy in the region. Also, until the 20th century, the address of the Kyrgyz fortress was called "Shahri Soman".

Kokildar House is an architectural monument located in Namuna village, Termiz city. Due to the renovation works carried out during the rule of the Timurids, it has reached its present magnificent state. It is a huge building with many rooms. It preserves strict proportion and symmetry [1]. Today, Kokildar family is making a great contribution to the development of tourism in Surkhandarya region. Among the people, Aloulmulk Khudovandzoda (the ruler of Termiz) was called "Azizon", "Azlar Eshon", "Kokildar" (coil cutting tool) (13th-16th centuries). The word Khanaqah means "room-thought" in Persian. At first, the abode built by Sufis and dervishes was called Khanaqah. Kokildar is the son-in-law of Hakim Termizi, the life partner of Huraida bint Muhammad al-Hakim. His real name is Somon Ashur Hamzai Hafiz Kokildar. He is also a scientist and the author of many works. At the age of 21, Somon Ashur grew his hair and went to Kyrgyz Castle to study under the pseudonym "Hamzai Hafiz Kokildar" in AD 952-953. In 966, he married Termizi's daughter, and then received permission to build the "Koshki Kokildar" mausoleum. But before the construction work was finished, in 980-981 AD, Somon Ashur died and was buried in his mausoleum.

Sultan Saodat complex is an architectural monument in Termiz (10th - 17th centuries). This shrine, located three kilometers northeast of Termiz, on the right bank of the Surkhan River, was formed over the course of 7 centuries. The Arabic name of Sultan Saodat or Sultan Sodot complex is Sultan al-Sador, and the Persian name is Sultan Sodot, which means Sultan of Sayyids. The complex is the dynastic mansion of the Sayyids of Termiz. Construction works were carried out between X-XIII centuries.

Zharkurgan tower is an architectural monument located in the village of Minor , Zharkurgan district , Surkhandarya region (1108-09) . It was built based on the traditions of the Khorasan school of architecture . Next to it was once the Jome mosque, built of baked bricks (not preserved). The Jarkurgan tower consists of 16 slab walls made of brick in the form of a wave on an 8-sided base . At a height of 20 m , arches with brick bars are made, and there is a belt border with Kufic inscriptions on it . The edges are continued above the belt, but the top of the tower is not preserved. The ruins of the mosque and minaret are depicted in the painting by N. N. Karazin (1879) . The current score of the tower. 21.6 m, the base (diameter - 5.4 m) has the name of the architect Ali ibn Muhammad Sarakhsi and the date of construction written on it (read by V. A. Shishkin). The Jarkurgan tower has been repaired and is protected by the state.

Historical monuments like this in Surkhandarya region greatly help the development of tourism. But the use of other attractive qualities plays an important role in strengthening their protection.

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